
APPLICATION OF SLIMS LIBRARY MANAGEMENT OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE

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Abstract:

Library is a place where knowledge resources are acquired, processed and preserved for the stakeholders and the future generations. The advent of information technology in the library management made its work more efficient and exhaustive. The purchase of readymade, vendor-based software is much expensive, so that a normal library having insufficient funds cannot go for its automation. But the emergence of open source movement made it possible to apply the library management software for its day-to-day activities with much impressive. SLIMS is one of the best open source software, which can be a boon to such small, under budget libraries. This paper highlights the characteristics and essentials of this software in the small libraries, like schools and public libraries.

Keywords: *Open source software (OSS); Library automation; Digitization; SLIMS Library management*

Introduction:

In the field of library science, the phrase "library automation" refers to the application of computers to carry out some of the most standard tasks associated with libraries, such stock checking, circulation, and cataloguing. The application of computer and networking technology in libraries is known as library automation. Thus, automation is the use of machinery to make work easier and conserve human energy and time.

The working environment in libraries has completely changed because to ICT. The majority of libraries today use computers to assist with their normal tasks, and this technology offers several advantages, including advancement, a reduction in work time and manpower

requirement, data protection and security, etc.

Application Open Source Software in Libraries:

With the development of open source software, the Internet has become a need in our day and age and has significantly aided the subject of library science (OSS). OSS are becoming common these days because of their enormous significance. The Open Source Software (OSS) offers free and simple access to the libraries, as well as the ability for users to make changes and modifications as well as run, copy, share, and develop the software as per needs. A system for organising and presenting information collections is presented by

open source library software. With data searching capabilities, it is easier to handle and maintain libraries and creating collections. They may also be automatically expanded and rebuilt, and they are simple to manage. Organizations now have unique options for purchasing and installing systems thanks to the abundance of Open Source Software (OSS) apps for library and information management. Applications of open source software for information management and library services will be covered in this paper.

Advantages of Open Source Software

Though there are some drawbacks of OSS, many advantages attract to it. These advantages are as follows.

1. Low cost or no cost software availability
2. Minimum hardware requirement
3. Technical support available from OSS communities
4. Compatible to universal database formats
5. Lowest threats of virus.
6. Customizable as per our needs.
7. Simple and easy to use.

Available Open Source software for Library Automation and Digitization:

There are ample of software available on internet with its source code. Various operating videos are also available on Youtube. Following are some selected library management and digital software which are known as open source software.

- a) Koha
- b) NewGenLib
- c) Evergreen
- d) Librarian
- e) OpenBiblio
- f) OPALS
- g) DSpace

- h) Greenstone
- i) Fedora
- j) E-Prints
- k) SLIMS9

SLIMS9: A Complete Solution (Open Source Software) for Small Libraries:

SLiMS releases are named after the local flora as a sign of respect and pride for Indonesia. Senayan Library Management System (SLiMS) is an open source library management software that was initially created in Indonesia with the help of numerous people from around the world, including Bangladesh. The software received a 2009 Indonesian ICT Award in the area of Open Source. Given that SLiMS was created using Unicode, it fully supports Bangla input and has excellent built-in features for both an institutional repository and a digital library.

Web-based Open Source Software (OSS) called SLiMS was created to address the needs of web-based library automation on a variety of scales, from small to large. SLiMS is appropriate for libraries with a variety of collections, several staff members, and a networked environment because it is fully featured and still being constantly developed, whether on a local network (intranet) or the Internet. Another benefit of SLiMS is that it can run natively across a wide range of operating systems that support the PHP programming language and MySQL RDBMS.

Special features of SLiMS:

- 1) Powerful Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC)
- 2) Standard data exchange with OAI PMH.
- 3) Data harvesting facility with Z39.50

- 4) Circulation system consisting with reservation, fine calculation facilities.
- 5) Member image capturing system directly from the machine camera.
- 6) Collection inventory (stock taking) function
- 7) Exhaustive reports generation systems.
- 8) Serial control management
- 9) Supporting various file formats.
- 10) Automatic barcode and QR code generation system
- 11) User ID generation facility
- 12) Library visitor counter

Pre-requisite for installation:

The following are requirements of SLIMS.

- a) Apache web server
- b) MySQL database
- c) PHP
- d) XAMPP Server

Though, there are some pre-requisites for the installation of this software, SLIMS has taken care of the common professionals. They have made available the ready to use software, for which one has to visit the website <https://slims.web.id/> and get download the software. It can be install on windows platform as well as on Linux also. As compare to Linux, the installation process is much easier in windows platform. Though this software does not follow MARC data format, it is most useful for small sized collection libraries such as school and public libraries.

Process of Installation SLIMS9 software on Windows platform:

Step 1) Download XAMPP Server from the website.

Step 2) Create a XAMPP folder in D Drive and paste this folder.

Step 3) Install this software.

Step 4) Open XAMPP Control panel

Step 5) Start Apache, MySQL & Tomcat

Step 6) Go to web browser and type

<http://127.0.0.1/phpmyadmin/>

Step 7) Create a database – slims9

Step 8) Install SLIMS9 from the website.

Step 9) Copy downloaded file and paste in D/XAMPP/htdocs

Step 10) Extract the zip file here

Step 11) Rename it as slims9

Step 12) Go to web browser and type

<http://127.0.0.1/slims9/>

Step 13) If an error arises, go to xampp control panel, and click CONFIG

PHP(phi.ini)

Step 14) find gd and remove ;

Step 15) Open web browser and type 127/0.0.1/slims9/admin

Conclusion:

In order to preserve library collections in a good manner and provide the number of library services using collected data, library automation is a powerful instrument in every library. To keep their consumer focus, libraries occasionally need to modify their technology. SLIMS will therefore be the best library management system for supporting all institutional libraries with the newest tools and services without breaking the bank.

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